

ALRIGH2T

Press Release

ALRIGH2T marks one year of progress: A big step in advancing innovative solutions for hydrogen-powered aviation

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- ALRIGH2T held its annual General Assembly in Vienna to review project progress and set the roadmap for the challenges of 2025.
- During the first year, the project reached a key milestone by conducting a preliminary analysis of refuelling technological concepts, evaluating their advantages and drawbacks.

The European project [ALRIGH2T](#) marked **the completion of its first year with a significant meeting in Vienna, Austria, from January 21st to 23rd, 2025**. The gathering brought together representatives from all partners, including academic institutions, airport operators, and leading companies in the hydrogen industry. This three-day event featured a joint workshop, organized in collaboration with the European project GOLIAT, aimed at fostering synergies and aligning objectives to position both projects within the liquid hydrogen and aircraft sectors.

Key achievements and challenges

The ALRIGH2T Project, launched in January 2024, has made steady advancements in its mission to develop and test innovative technologies and processes for refuelling liquid hydrogen (LH2) aircraft under real airport conditions. Over the past twelve months, the strong collaboration among project partners has been instrumental in establishing the framework for demonstration activities at two key airports in Milan (Italy) and Paris (France). Notably, substantial progress has been achieved in defining technical specifications and outlining techno-economic boundary conditions.

One of the major milestones of this first year has been the pre-analysis of refuelling technological concepts. As part of this effort, a SWOT analysis was conducted to evaluate two different refuelling approaches, identifying their respective strengths and limitations. Additionally, LH2 demand models were developed, taking into account medium- and short-haul aircraft routes from Milan Malpensa and Paris airports. These models estimate future LH2 requirements up to the year 2035, providing a foundation for infrastructure planning.

Building on previous progress, **a new prototype pump** capable of refuelling aircraft with subcooled LH2 has reached an advanced stage. The mechanical design of the pump has been finalized, and dynamic modelling of the LH2 loading and offloading process is progressing. Moreover, the project collaborators have completed the subsystem identification and have carried out initial pump models along with dynamic simulations of the connection line and receiving tank.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 101138105.

For the direct refuelling system, significant advancements have also been made. First, the **design of the SAG Basic Tank**, equipped with integrated additional sensors, has been completed. The team has conducted material selection tests for the sensor support components and finalized preliminary CFD multiphase simulations for the digital twin of the refuelling system. In addition, **the teams responsible have defined the coupling strategy for integrating different system models** and established the principal setup of the control system for the SAG test.

In recent months, the Italian Civil Aviation Authority (ENAC) has been involved in discussions regarding permitting activities for the upcoming demonstration at Milan Malpensa Airport. A **“sandbox procedure”** will soon be activated and this will lead, through close dialogue with the authority, to defining the testing sequence, ensuring a structured and coordinated approach to implementation.

Despite these achievements, the ALRIGH2T Project faced an unexpected challenge with the bankruptcy and liquidation of one of its main industrial partners, Universal Hydrogen. This company was responsible for tank swap technology and the planned hydrogen demonstration at Paris Airport. In response, the project consortium has conducted a thorough evaluation of the potential impacts and is actively exploring alternative solutions to mitigate disruptions. Innovative proposals are currently being developed to ensure the project's continued progress.

Collaborative workshop with the GOLIAT Project

The second in-person meeting of the ALRIGH2T project took place at the facilities of the Austrian Technological Institute (AIT) on January 21st and the morning of January 22nd, 2025. The meeting was focused on reviewing key advances, discussing major takeaways, addressing recent and upcoming challenges, and defining the next steps for the project.

To make the most of the partners' presence in Vienna, **a workshop was organized** on the afternoon of January 22nd and the morning of January 23rd, **in collaboration with the European GOLIAT Project**, an innovative aviation hydrogen handling and refuelling initiative that closely aligns with ALRIGH2T's objectives. The workshop provided an open platform for around 50 participants to explore crucial topics relevant to both projects, such as analysis and authorization procedures for proposed demonstrations, techno-economic assessment challenges, the identification of standardization gaps, the development of common roadmaps, and shared technological challenges.

After three days of fruitful discussions, the **Project Coordinator of ALRIGH2T, [ENEA](#)**, expressed satisfaction with the positive results of the gathering, “after one year of work and despite the challenge of the difficult situation caused by the loss of a really relevant partner, during the General Assembly the consortium could meet face to face, networking together and focusing on its objectives and future proposals. We also had the opportunity to host the first joint workshop and start concretely building up cooperation with the EU project GOLIAT realizing how much the two sister projects were linked, complementing each other in several fields”.

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As the project moves forward, the commitment of all partners remains strong, driving the development of pioneering LH2 refuelling solutions that will support the future of sustainable aviation.

ALRIGH2T partners at the M12 General Assembly in Vienna, Austria.

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Contact

Press officer:

Ana Báscones abascones@zabala.es

Phone number: M (+34) 673 744 543

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